

ISic3660

I.Sicily inscription 3660

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tufa arenaria

Object

aedicula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi, inventory 4538

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR108279

1. Αριθμ μακαρῖτα

2. χ[α]ῖρε

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 108279

Bibliography

Gabrics, E. 1929. Stele sepolcrali di Lilibeo a forma di Heroon. *Monumenti Antichi*. 33: 41-60. At 58-59

Bisi, A.M. 1970. Influenze italiote e siceliote sull'arte tardo-punica. Le stele

funerarie di Lilibeo. *Archeologia Classica*. 22: 92-130. At 105 no.14 tav.53.2
Vento, M. 2000. Le stele dipinte di Lilibeo. Marsala. At 47-50 tav.1-4

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